

Study the Diagnostic Role of Fnac in Thyroid Lesion by the Bethesda System for Reporting Thyroid Cytopathology (TBSRTC)**Renu Sahay¹, Mayank Kumar Singh², Ramji Verma³, Sufia Ahmad Khan⁴, Jitendra Singh Yadav⁵**¹Professor, Department of Pathology, M.L.B, Medical College, Jhansi, UP, India²Professor & Head, Department of Pathology, M.L.B, Medical College, Jhansi, UP, India³Junior Resident, Department of Pathology, M.L.B, Medical College, Jhansi, UP, India⁴Associate Professor, Department of Pathology, M.L.B, Medical College, Jhansi, UP, India⁵Professor, Department of Otorhinolaryngology, Maharani Laxmi Bai Medical College, Jhansi, UP, India

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Abstract:**Background:** When assessing thyroid lesions, Fine-Needle Aspiration Cytology (FNAC) is a crucial diagnostic technique. To help standardize reporting and clinical care, thyroid FNAC data are divided into six diagnostic groups using the Bethesda System for Reporting Thyroid Cytopathology (TBSRTC). This study aims to evaluate the diagnostic role of FNAC in thyroid lesions using TBSRTC and correlate with cytohistological correlation.**Methods:** A prospective and retrospective study was conducted at the Department of Pathology, Maharani Laxmi Bai Medical College, Jhansi, on 350 patients with palpable thyroid swellings who underwent FNAC, followed by thyroidectomy for histopathological correlation in 60 cases. FNAC samples were categorized according to TBSRTC, and statistical analysis was performed to calculate sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), negative predictive value (NPV), and diagnostic accuracy.**Results:** The mean age of the study population was 37.50±14.14 years, and 82.29% of the participants were female. The majority of cases (72.29%) had nodular thyroid swellings upon presentation. The accuracy of FNAC samples was 96.57%. The sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV, and diagnostic accuracy of FNAC were calculated based on histopathological correlation.**Conclusion:** As classified by TBSRTC, FNAC is a cost-effective, minimally invasive, and dependable diagnostic method for thyroid lesions. It helps reduce needless procedures, guide clinical management, and differentiate benign from malignant lesions. The study confirms the usefulness of TBSRTC in offering consistent and repeatable thyroid cytopathology diagnostic standards.**Keywords:** FNAC; thyroid lesions; Bethesda System; cytopathology; thyroid nodule; diagnostic accuracy.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Thyroid swellings are a common clinical finding that affects 4-7% of the general population. The prevalence is higher in females than in males. Its frequency in iodine-deficient areas can reach up to 25%, and it rises with age, goitrogenic substances in the diet, and a history of radiation exposure [1-2]. In India, more than 42 million people have goiter, and there are more than 2 billion instances worldwide [3]. Thyroid cancer is the most prevalent endocrine system cancer, making up 1% of all cancers [4].

The majority of nodules are benign lesions, but in order to differentiate them from malignancy, a number of diagnostic tests, including USG, nuclear scan, and FNAC, are helpful in identifying patients who require surgery [5]. In the 1950s, FNAC was

introduced in Scandinavian countries. By the 1970s, it had gained popularity in the United States, and by the 1980s, it had spread throughout the world [6]. According to recent research, FNAC is the gold standard for diagnosing thyroid nodules since it is easy to use, accurate, and most importantly, affordable. To prevent needless surgery, it is crucial to distinguish benign lesions before surgery [5].

In the past, thyroid FNAC reporting patterns were inconsistent across various cytopathologists and labs, which caused doctors to misread results and administer treatment ineffectively. The National Cancer Institute in Bethesda, Maryland, implemented the Bethesda System for Reporting Thyroid Cytopathology (TBSRTC) in 2007 as a

solution to this problem. The thyroid lesions' FNAC is divided into six diagnostic categories by TBSRTC, each of which has distinct cancer risks and obvious recommendations for additional therapeutic treatment. These include benign, atypical follicular lesion of unknown significance (AFLUS), "suspicious" for follicular neoplasm (SFN), suspicious for malignancy (SM), malignant, and non-diagnostic/unsatisfactory [7].

Even though FNAC and TBSRTC are widely used, diagnostic ambiguity is caused by differences in cytological interpretation, FNAC sensitivity limitations, and doubts about the therapeutic relevance of specific TBSRTC categories. Research is still being done to determine how best to use molecular testing in the TBSRTC framework. The purpose of the study was to classify the thyroid lesions based on TBSRTC, then correlate the cytohisto for statistical analysis and malignancy risk.

Material and Methods

A Prospective, retrospective study was conducted in the department of Pathology, MLB Medical College, Jhansi, from May 2023 to July 2024. The study was approved by the institute's ethics council and included all thyroid lesions that underwent thyroid fine-needle aspiration cytology (FNAC).

The study included all patients, regardless of age or sex, who had thyroid swellings that were clinically palpable. Patients who (1) refused to have FNAC for thyroid lesions despite being informed of the procedure's goal, benefits, and potential side effects, and (2) had parathyroid, lymph node, and other surrounding structure lesions were excluded.

Records of patients who had thyroid FNAC were gathered from the files for the retrospective study. A pre-made proforma was used to record the clinical history, physical examination results, and preliminary clinical diagnosis for prospective cases prior to FNA. Prior to their inclusion in the trial, all patients provided written informed consent.

For FNAC 23G needles and disposable syringes with a capacity of 10 cc or 20 cc were used under aseptic conditions. There were two or three passes. Fluid was aspirated if the edema was cystic. The aspirated material was promptly placed onto glass slides, half of which were fixed with alcohol for Papanicolaou stain and half of which were allowed to air dry. Either ultrasound guidance or no guidance is used during the FNAC technique to get the aspirate. The Bethesda technique for reporting thyroid lesions was used to examine the stained smears. Paraffin blocks and slides were obtained from the Department of Pathology and examined for cases that were retrospective. All surgical specimens for potential cases were received in neutral buffered formalin (10%). The results of the

surgical specimens' gross examination were recorded. Following tissue processing, slices were cut using a microtome and assessed using the Hematoxylin and Eosin staining procedure. Numerous thyroid lesions were analyzed in connection to age and gender, and cytohistological correlation was performed in each case.

Non-diagnostic or unsatisfactory: If a smear did not meet the Bethesda system's adequacy requirements, it was classified as non-diagnostic [8]. A specimen was deemed sufficient for a solid nodule if it included at least six follicular groups with at least 10 cells that were well-preserved and stained. On the other hand, a colloid nodule's plentiful thick colloid did not require a minimum number of follicular cells. Histiocyte-containing thyroid cysts that lacked follicular cells were considered non-diagnostic. An aspirate smear containing significant cytological atypia, was never considered inadequate, regardless of cellularity.

Benign: If a case exhibited the cytomorphological characteristics of adenomatoid goiter or colloid goiter, Hashimoto's thyroiditis, thyrotoxicosis, de Quervain's thyroiditis, or granulomatous thyroiditis as a result of Koch's, it was considered benign.

Atypia of undetermined significance/atypical follicular lesion of undetermined significance: According to the Bethesda System's standards, aspirates that were deemed sufficient and had certain atypia-related characteristics but could not be definitively classified into the benign, SFN, SM, or malignancy categories were placed under this category [9]. For instance, AFLUS was identified in a smear that displayed high cellularity, small follicular cells grouped in sheets, clusters, or singly, with sporadic multinucleated large cells and focal Hurthle cell occurrence.

Follicular neoplasm/suspicious for follicular neoplasm: This category included aspirates with cytomorphologic characteristics of moderate to high cellularity, little or no colloid, and a mostly microfollicular or trabecular arrangement of follicular cells in a repeating pattern. This category includes included aspirates with Hurthle cellneoplasm cytomorphologic characteristics.

Suspicious for malignancy: This group included aspirates with cytological characteristics that were suggestive of papillary carcinoma, medullary carcinoma, or lymphoma but not conclusive of any of these conditions [10]. An aspirate was deemed suspicious for medullary carcinoma, for instance, if it contained cytological features of high cellularity, elongated oblong cells with sporadic plasmacytoid appearance, some cells exhibiting Hurthle cell change, and a matrix distinct from colloid, possibly amyloid.

Malignant: This group included aspirates that seemed to be categorically malignant [11].

Statistical Analysis: SPSS version 25.0 was used for the statistical analysis. Whereas categorical data were displayed as frequencies and percentages, continuous variables, such as age, were represented by the mean, median, and standard deviation (SD).

MedCalc's Diagnostic Test Evaluation tool was used to determine the sensitivity, specificity, accuracy, positive predictive value, negative predictive value, and risk of malignancy for FNAs using the Bethesda method in cases with surgical follow-up. Nodules identified as FN/SFN, suspected for malignancy, or malignant that were confirmed to be malignant by histology were considered true positives, whereas nodules with benign FNA cytology and surgical pathology were considered true negatives. When cytological results suggested FN/SFN, were questionable for

malignancy, or were malignant, they were classified as false positives upon surgical removal. Cases with benign cytology that turned out to be malignant on histology were examples of false negatives.

Results

A total of 350 cases of thyroid FNAC were collected and categorized according to the Bethesda system for reporting cytopathology (TBSRBC 2023). Study shows predominance of cases in 31-40 years age group with 31.14% of cases with a mean age of 37.50 years.

A female cases were found to be 82.29%. Nodular thyroid swellings was found in 72.29% cases and diffuse thyroid swellings in 23.71%. Only 4.00% cases were from solitary thyroid swellings (4.00%). Out of 250 cases, 338 cases (96.57%) were satisfactory for cytological assessment, while 12 cases (3.43%) were non-satisfactory (Table 1).

Table 1: Demographic profile of cases

Parameters	No. of cases	Percentage
Age (mean ±SD) yrs	37.50±14.14	
Gender		
Male	62	17.71
Female	288	82.29
Thyroid swelling		
Diffused	83	23.71
Nodular	253	72.29
Solitary	14	4.00
Adequacy		
Satisfactory	338	96.57
Non satisfactory	12	3.43

The results shows that the most of the cases, 90.57%, were classified as benign (Category II), while non-diagnostic cases (Category I) constituted 3.43%. Atypia of undetermined significance (Category III) and follicular neoplasm (Category

IV) represented 0.86% and 1.43% of the cases, respectively.

Suspicious for malignancy (Category V) and malignant cases (Category VI) were 0.57% and 3.14%, respectively (Table 2).

Table 2: Distribution of cases according to Bethesda categories in FNAC (n=350)

Grade	Bethesda categories	Number of patients	Percentage (%)
I	Non diagnostic	12	3.43%
II	Benign	317	90.57%
III	Atypia of undetermined significance	3	0.86%
IV	Follicular neoplasm	5	1.43%
V	Suspicious for malignancy	2	0.57%
VI	Malignant	11	3.14%
	Total	350	100%

Bethesda Category I (Non-diagnostic) included 12 cases (3.43%), primarily due to acellular samples and obscuring blood. Bethesda Category II (Benign) was the most common, with 317 cases (90.57%), comprising Follicular Nodules with Colloid Nodules, Chronic Lymphocytic (Hashimoto) Thyroiditis, and Hyperplastic Goiter

among others. Bethesda Category III (Atypia of Undetermined Significance) had 3 cases (0.86%), while Bethesda Category IV (Follicular Neoplasm) included 5 cases (1.43%). Bethesda Category V (Suspicious for Malignancy) had 2 cases (0.57%), and Bethesda Category VI (Malignant) comprised 11 cases (3.14%), with diagnoses of Papillary

Thyroid Carcinoma and Anaplastic Thyroid Carcinoma (Table 3) (Figure 1,2 &3).

Table 3: Distribution of the individual thyroid lesion according to Bethesda categories on FNAC (n=350)

Bethesda categories	Number of case in each category	Cytological diagnosis	Number of case	%	Total %
I	12	Non diagnostic (Fluid only)	3	0.86%	3.43%
		Non diagnostic (Acellular)	4	1.14%	
		Non diagnostic (Obscuring blood)	5	1.43%	
II	317	FND-CN	74	21.14%	90.57%
		FND-CNCD	101	28.86%	
		FND-AN	32	9.14%	
		FND-MNG	2	0.57%	
		CL-HT	94	26.86%	
		GT	2	0.57%	
		PH-GD	12	3.43%	
III	3	AUS	3	0.86%	0.86%
IV	5	FN	5	1.43%	1.43%
V	2	SFM	2	0.57%	0.57%
VI	11	PTC	9	2.57%	3.14%
		ATC	2	0.57%	
Total	350		350	100%	100%

Out of 60 thyroidectomy specimens, 47 cases (78.33%) were non-neoplastic, including conditions like colloid nodules and hyperplastic nodules and 13 cases (21.67%) were neoplastic, with both benign neoplasms such as follicular adenoma and malignant ones like papillary thyroid carcinoma (Table 4).

Table 4: The number of cases studied by histopathology examination of neoplastic and non- neoplastic specimen (n=60)

Type of Lesion in Histology	Number of patients	Percentage (%)
Non Neoplastic	47	78.33%
Neoplastic	13	21.67%
Total	60	100%

In Bethesda Category I (Non-diagnostic), no surgical specimens were received. In Bethesda Category II (Benign), out of 46 surgical specimens, the histopathological diagnoses included colloid nodules (25 cases, 41.67%), colloid nodules with cystic degeneration/multinodular goiter (16 cases, 26.67%), hyperplastic nodules (3 cases, 6.67%), and chronic lymphocytic thyroiditis (2 cases, 3.33%), all of which were concordant with the cytological diagnosis. For Bethesda Category III (Atypia of Undetermined Significance), 2 surgical specimens were received; one was diagnosed as follicular adenoma (1.67%) and the other as

hyperplastic nodule (1.67%), showing one concordant and one discordant case. In Bethesda Category IV (Follicular Neoplasm), 3 surgical specimens were analyzed, with 2 cases of follicular adenoma (3.33%) and 1 case of papillary thyroid carcinoma (1.67%), both concordant with cytology. Bethesda Category V (Suspicious for Malignancy) had 1 surgical specimen, which was diagnosed as papillary thyroid carcinoma (1.67%), concordant with cytology. Finally, in Bethesda Category VI (Malignant), 8 surgical specimens were received, all diagnosed as papillary thyroid carcinoma (13.33%) (Table 5).

Table 5: Comparison of cytological diagnosis with final histological diagnosis with remark and incidence of malignancy in each Bethesda category

Bethesda categories On FNAC	No. of surgical specimens received (n=)	Histopathological diagnosis	No. of cases	%	Concordant/ Discordant
ND (n=12)	0	-	-	-	-
Benign (n=317)	46	CND	25	41.67%	Concordant
		CNCD/MNG	16	26.67%	Concordant
		Hyperplastic nodule	3	6.67%	Concordant
		CLT	2	3.33%	Concordant
AUS (n=3)	2	Follicular adenoma	1	1.67%	Concordant
		Hyperplastic nodule	1	1.67%	Discordant

FN (n=5)	3	Follicular adenoma Papillary thyroid carcinoma	2 1	3.33% 1.67%	Concordant Concordant
SFM (n=2)	1	Papillary thyroid carcinoma	1	1.67%	Concordant
Malignant (n=11)	8	Papillary thyroid carcinoma	8	13.33%	Concordant
Total (n=350)	60		60	100%	-

Category I had a 0.00% ROM, compared to the TBSRTC proposed range of 5-20%. Category II also had a 0.00% ROM, against the proposed 2-7%. For Category III, the ROM was 0.00%, while the TBSRTC proposed 13-30%. In Category IV, the ROM was 33.00%, slightly higher than the

TBSRTC's 23-34%. Category V had a 100% ROM, compared to the proposed 67-83%. Lastly, Category VI also showed a 100% ROM, aligning with the TBSRTC's proposed range of 97-100% (Table 6).

Table 6: Comparison of category wise risk of malignancy (ROM) with TBSRTC on, cytohistopathological correlation

Diagnosis category	ROM of present study (%)	Proposed ROM by TBSRTC % (range)
Category I	0.00%	13 (5-20)
Category II	0.00%	4 (2-7)
Category III	0.00%	22 (13-30)
Category IV	33.00%	30 (23-34)
Category V	100%	74 (67-83)
Category VI	100%	97 (97-100)

Figure 1 : (A) Colloid nodule with cystic degeneration (MGG- 40X); (B): Colloid nodule with hemosiderin foamy macrophage (H&E-10X); (C) Chronic Lymphocytic thyroiditis (MGG-40X); (D) Hashimoto's thyroiditis with hurthle cell changes (MGG-40x).

Figure 2: (A) Granulomatous thyroiditis (MGG-40X); (B) Atypia undetermined of significance (MGG-40X); (C) Follicular neoplasm (PAP-40X); (D) Follicular adenoma (H&E-10X)

Figure 3: (A) Papillary carcinoma (PAP-10X); (B) Papillary carcinoma (Intranuclear cytoplasmic inclusions) (MGG-40X); (C) Papillary carcinoma (H&E-40X); (D) Undifferentiated (Anaplastic) carcinoma (MGG-40X)

Discussion

Thyroid disorders are very important because the majority can be managed with medication or surgery. A useful diagnostic technique is fine needle aspiration cytology. It aids in the triage of thyroid nodule patients to determine which ones need surgical treatment. There was a great deal of misunderstanding about how to treat thyroid nodules because of the inconsistent reporting of thyroid cytology in the past. It appeared more straightforward, methodical, and clear when we documented the diagnosis using the standards outlined in the Bethesda system's standardized nomenclature; as a result, it would be more helpful in directing medical professionals in the treatment of thyroid nodules.[12] The Bethesda system for reporting cytopathology (TBSRTC 2023) was used in 350 thyroid FNAC cases for this study. Histopathological analysis and cytology correlation were performed on the cases that had undergone thyroid surgery.

Thyroid lesions predominantly affect middle-aged individuals as we reported mean age of cases were 37.50 years, results supported by the study of Dhamecha M. P. et al[13]. In our study FNAC for thyroid lesions, a significant female predominance (82.29%) compared to males (17.71%) were observed in this study which aligns with the findings of similar studies, such as those by DiptiSidam et al. (2020) [14] and Keval A Patel et al. (2021)[15] who reported 85.0% and 89.75% of females cases.

This study illustrates the prevalence of benign conditions in thyroid lesions and the usefulness of the Bethesda System in accurately stratifying the risk of malignancy, thereby guiding clinical management decisions. Approximately 90.57% of cases were classified as benign, while 3.43% were non-diagnostic. Furthermore, comparable to the 90.57% revealed in our analysis, a study by Choudhury et al.[16] discovered that 85.2% of FNAC cases were benign. Our study's malignancy rates (3.14%) are in line with those of Bakiarathana et al. [17], who discovered that 2.8% of their sample had malignant cases.

In this study, histopathological examination of 60 thyroidectomy specimens showed that non-neoplastic lesions accounted for 78.33% of the total cases, with colloid nodules being the most prevalent. Malignant neoplasms like papillary thyroid carcinoma and benign neoplasms like follicular adenoma made up 21.67% of the neoplastic lesions.

Colloid goiter was the most common diagnosis in a research by Patel et al. (2021)[18] that examined 276 thyroid FNAC cases and discovered that 85.9% of them were benign. A significant rate of concordance with histological findings was seen in

this study for benign patients (Bethesda Category II), especially for colloid nodules and multinodular goiters. There was some discordance in cases of atypia of uncertain significance (AUS), which suggests that thorough follow-up is necessary. The high rate of concordance between the suspected for malignancy (SFM) and follicular neoplasms (FN) categories highlights the accuracy of FNAC in predicting these disorders. The accuracy of FNAC in identifying malignancy was validated by histology, which confirmed all instances classified as malignant (Category VI). These findings are in line with the research conducted by Ravetto et al. (2000)[19], which found that FNAC had high accuracy and predictive values, especially for malignant lesions.

A category-wise risk of malignancy (ROM) for thyroid lesions, revealing a 0.00% ROM for non-diagnostic, benign, and atypia of undetermined significance categories, lower than the TBSRTC proposed ranges of 5-20%, 2-7%, and 13-30%, respectively. However, the ROM for follicular neoplasm was 33.00%, aligning with the TBSRTC range of 23-34%, and the ROM for suspicious for malignancy and malignant categories were both 100%, exceeding the TBSRTC ranges of 67-83% and 97-100%.

These findings indicate high diagnostic accuracy and reliability of FNAC, particularly for higher-risk categories. Compared to the study by Garg et al. (2015)[20], which reported ROMs of 10% for non-diagnostic, 2% for benign, 15% for atypia of undetermined significance, 28% for follicular neoplasm, 75% for suspicious for malignancy, and 98% for malignant categories, this study shows a consistently lower ROM in lower-risk categories and comparable results in higher-risk categories, emphasizing the effectiveness of the Bethesda System in predicting malignancy and guiding clinical management.

Conclusion

An efficient and reasonably method for diagnosing thyroid nodules is fine needle aspiration cytology. For a systematic method of reporting thyroid cytopathology, the Bethesda system is highly helpful. In order to prevent unnecessary surgeries, this reporting system also evaluates the risk of malignancy.

There was less overall histopathology follow-up in our study. Finding interpretation problems will be made easier with improved follow-up. However, a prospective study over a larger population would lend more insight into the merits and demerits of the proposed system.

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